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PEST ORGANISMS THREATENING EUROPE

XF-ACTORS

XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA ACTIVE CONTAINMENT
THROUGH A MULTIDISCIPLINARY-ORIENTED RESEARCH STRATEGY

3RD JOINT ANNUAL MEETING

Xylella Fastidiosa Active Containment Through a
multidisciplinary-Oriented Research Strategy

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

AJACCIO (FRANCE), 28–30 OCTOBER 2019

**PALAIS DES CONGRÈS, QUAI L'HERMINIER
AJACCIO, FRANCE**

THE EVENT WAS PART OF THE SECOND SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE ON ONGOING RESEARCH INTO *X. FASTIDIOSA* CO-ORGANISED WITH EUROPEAN FOOD SAFETY AUTHORITY (EFSA), H2020-MSCA-RISE PROJECT 734353 'CURE-XF', COST ACTION CA16107 'EUROXANTH', FRENCH NATIONAL INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH (INRA), FRENCH AGENCY FOR FOOD, ENVIRONMENTAL AND OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY (ANSES), EUPHRESKO, OFFICE DE L'ENVIRONNEMENT DE LA CORSE-DEPARTMENT CONSERVATOIRE BOTANIQUE NATIONAL DE CORSE (OEC-CNBC)

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Poster

Specific PCR detection of *Pseudophaeomoniella* spp. in the xylem of healthy and *Xylella fastidiosa*-infected olive trees

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Abstract: Several fungal species have been found associated with the olive quick decline syndrome (OQDS) caused by *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca* (Xfp) in Apulia, southern Italy. The xylem-inhabiting species, *Pseudophaeomoniella oleae* and *Ps. oleicola*, were associated with brown or black wood streaking of various olive varieties, both on young and centenarian trees. However, specific pathogenicity tests conducted on olive plantlets indicated that these fungal species have a marginal role in the aetiology of OQDS. Considering the wide distribution of *Ps. oleae* and *Ps. oleicola* over the olive-growing areas in Apulia, a genomic characterisation study was started, in order to investigate the biology of these fungi, and to ascertain any possible interaction with Xfp and the OQDS. Several PCR primers were designed from the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) regions of the rDNA genes of *Pseudophaeomoniella* spp. in order to develop a species-specific detection method. Primers were screened against the two reference strains, *Ps. oleae* FV84 and *Ps. oleicola* M24, and six more *Pseudophaeomoniella* spp. isolates, resulting in the amplification of a single specific amplicon from most of the primer pairs tested. Fifteen primer pairs confirmed their specificity when tested against several isolates of different xylem-inhabiting fungal genera, such as *Phaeoacremonium*, *Pleurostomophora*, *Phaeomoniella*, *Ochroconis*, *Paraconiothydium*, *Aspergillus*, *Lophiostoma* and *Cladosporium* spp. The size of the obtained amplicons enabled the use of some primer pairs in a real-time PCR test, using a SYBR® Green format. Results confirmed the specificity of the tested primers, thus allowing the detection and quantification of *Ps. oleae* and *Ps. oleicola*, into the xylem of both healthy and Xfp-infected olive trees. Further research is in progress to develop a specific probe for qPCR quantification of the targeted fungal species in the olive plant.